

Discussion paper: ICU acquired illness as a cause of death or complications with long-term Covid 19 patients.

MTE Kahn

In Wuhan, China, during December 2019, a number of cases of severe pneumonia were found, associated with the Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market. The World Health Organization (WHO) named the new virus associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 19 (SARS Cov-19) (Garcia, PDW et al, 2020). Up to this day of writing, the coronavirus-disease-2019 (COVID-19) has caused more than 2,6 million deaths worldwide. I am an Engineer by profession, not a medical doctor, so I am not going to make sweeping remarks on a profession that I do honour yet have some serious points of criticism or concerns to raise against, just as they are welcome to raise if we, as engineers, fail to be compliant and aeroplanes fall from the sky or bridges collapse. This is an essay to understand and raise concern; to get in touch with the fading human element of care that has been replaced with curtains of fear, unaccountable practices, and voodoo treatments in the face of a life-threatening disease. Fungal and Bacterial co-infection have been found in patients with COVID-19, but there is, as yet, limited experience on these infections in critically ill patients in the ICU. Herewith I present what I see as three aspects, which in a logical observation, clearly affect Covid-19 ICU mortalities, yet will rarely be held as even possible causes of unwarranted deaths. It is an age in which everything is written off, once you enter that ICU doors, as death by COVID-19.

Hospital-acquired infections

Improvement in hand-hygiene compliance is important for reducing cross-infection by micro-organisms. COVID-19 is associated with a high disease burden with 10% of confirmed cases progressing towards critical illness. Nevertheless, the disease course and predictors of mortality in critically ill patients are poorly understood. This is often not very well explained by the medical fraternity. A study by De Mortel (2008) found that “Nosocomial infections (NI’s) increase morbidity and mortality rates and the cost of health care. Although infection rates often decline with increasing hand-hygiene frequency, average hand-hygiene compliance by health care workers (HCW) is poor.”

In a European study published in 2020, for a well risk defined scenario under high levels of hygiene, ICU-mortality was 24% of a cohort of 639 critically ill patients with confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection. The median length of stay in hospital was 12 days (IQR, 5 21). Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) was diagnosed in 74% of the 639 patients, with a minimum P/F-ratio of 110 (IQR, 80 148) (Garcia, PDW et al., 2020).

In another study based in Taiwan, it was found that there was no significant difference between the number of inpatient infections for days in 2020, 2019, and 2018. It was established that, due to the higher risk of healthcare workers, the consumption of either alcohol for hand-hygiene or surgical masks significantly increased in 2020. However, the overall Hospital Acquired Infection incidence density did not significantly differ from the rate at the baseline period (Lo et al., 2021). Now what does this mean? Hospital Acquired Infections (HAI) occurred at roughly the same rate during pre-Covid-19. Couple that with critically ill ARDS patients, and catheter-induced or even orally-acquired glove contamination by nursing staff could pose serious threats. With hospital staff overworked due to increasing Covid patient numbers, this is not a pretty picture to unfold.

The Taiwanese study mentions that during the 2003 Hong Kong SARS outbreak, an increase in Certain HAI were noticed in an ICU when gloves and gowns were worn all the time (Yap et al., 2004). The change in occurrence of Multiple Drug Resistant Organisms (MDRO) was different between hospitals as varied infection control measures were applied. For the current COVID-19 situation, most staff have been hyper-aware. This is especially relevant for healthcare workers, concerning hand-hygiene, glove-use, and glove replacements among other infection control activities. In the Hong Kong study, the use of hand soap did not differ from previous years without SARS. However, this may have been due to hand-hygiene in hospitals being performed by the dry clean method via alcohol.

During the same period, inpatients' medical conditions were generally more severe and showed more co-morbidities that required medical care. In this way, severely ill patients will clearly be more susceptible to infection. This will explain the lack of significant change in the HAI rate, whereas respiratory and hand hygiene was improved.

What then are hospital-acquired infections?

Forty years after the introduction of intensive care units in hospitals, the necessity of handwashing remains a tenet of hospital hygiene, and the prevalence of nosocomial infections are viewed as markers of poor compliance with hand-hygiene requirements. There is a widely held belief that handwashing is effective and an 'all-or-nothing' intervention. Sax et al. (2009) re-iterate that hand-hygiene, and by extension glove-hygiene, is the single most important element necessary for the prevention of nosocomial infections as it holds the greatest risk of **transferring germs from one surface to another**.

Bardi et al. (2021) conducted an intense study of nosocomial infections in ICU facilities for COVID-19 treatment. The study was a retrospective single-centre, case-control study with a sample of 140 patients with severe COVID-19 admitted to the ICU during 2020. The investigation targeted clinical, epidemiological, and microbiological cases in light of HAI in the ICU. The results were shocking. Fifty-seven patients (40.7%) developed a bacterial or fungal nosocomial infection during their ICU stay. The Bardi et al. (2021) study found that infection occurred after a median of nine days of admission. Of these hospital-acquired infections, 31% were primary and 25% were catheter-related bloodstream infections. These were the most frequent. The next layer of infections were hospital-acquired pneumonia (23%), tracheobronchitis (10%), and urinary tract infection (8%) that were produced by a wide spectrum of Gram-positive (55%) and Gram-negative bacteria (30%) as well as fungi (15%) transmitted in various ways to patients. In 60% of cases, infection was associated with septic shock. These infections were significantly linked with death and a longer ICU stay. This study is an honest and very clearly reported study that links hospital-acquired bacterial and fungal nosocomial infection as a common complication of ICU admission in patients with COVID-19. Such cases usually present as a severe form of infection with the presence of Coronavirus, and it is associated with a high mortality and longer course of ICU stay (Bardi et al., 2021).

Hospital-acquired influenza is a particular problem in some patients. Influenza was laboratory-confirmed at a rate of 9% of patients during their hospitalization. Having been admitted to hospital with an underlying disease was an important characteristic of hospital-acquired cases of influenza-like-illness. Cardiovascular disease was the most frequent underlying condition in both influenza-positive and influenza-negative patients. The site of the most influenza incidence rate was the greatest in number in the geriatric ward (Guerche-Seblain et al., 2020).

A particular hospital spreader is **Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase-Producing Enterobacteria** (ESBL-PE). The number of ESBL-PE carriers has also dramatically increased worldwide and is spread to the community via hospitals. ESBL-PE infections are associated with prolonged hospital stay; outcomes of its effect on mortality are attributed, at least in part, to improper treatment of this hospital-acquired illness.

Other nasties of the MDRO are with reference to four major pathogens such as **Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus aureus** (MRSA), **Carbapenem-Resistant Pseudomonas Aeruginosa** (CRPA), **Carbapenem-Resistant Acinetobacter Baumannii** (CRAB), and **Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococcus** (VRE). The incidence density of each Hospital Acquired Infection (HAI) includes complications of the respiratory tract, bloodstream infections, urinary tract infections, and surgical site infections.

Hospital hygiene

Wearing PPE is a huge matter nowadays and nowhere is this more accentuated than in the ICU setting where patients are housed for COVID-19 treatments. It is thought that wearing gloves reduces the risk of hand infection to healthcare personnel after contact with patients and may reduce the risk of the transmission of pathogens from patient to patient. Yet, despite this, the World Health Organization has declared nosocomial infections a serious global problem that increases the duration of hospitalization, creates difficulties in the course of patient treatment, increases expenditures, and threatens the life of individuals. In a 2016 study by researchers in Iran, the rate of nosocomial infections is up to 7 times higher in patients admitted to intensive care units (ICUs) compared with patients admitted to other hospital wards. It is here where good hand-hygiene comes to the fore as a primary and crucial tool for reducing infections caused by healthcare personnel. It is only logical that the mere wearing of gloves alone is not effective in reducing the transmission of infections to other patients. The Iranian study showed that there is a general lack of information on the level of hand-hygiene compliance among healthcare professionals, especially those in ICUs. The researchers conducted a study to measure hand-hygiene compliance based on before-and-after wearing of gloves among ICU nurses in the hospitals in Iran. They found that wearing gloves alone is not sufficient to prevent infection transmission between patients, and gloves may carry microbial agents excreted from a patient's body. The study, done in 2016, found that hand-hygiene compliance was poor among ICU nurses before wearing gloves and they mostly wore gloves without first washing their hands. Gloves, therefore, protect the ICU worker, but not necessarily the patient (Azam Ghorbani et al., 2016).

Another research project had as its objective the conduction of an observational study to measure how the improper use of gloves limits compliance to hand-hygiene and exposes patient's to infection. This study was done in France, conducted in five wards (three intensive care units and two medical wards) of a French university hospital. A hundred-and-twenty (120) healthcare workers were observed in staff-patient and staff-environment contacts for patients colonized or infected with pathogenic bacteria. Hand-hygiene was not undertaken due to improper gloving in 64.4% of instances. Microbial transmission have occurred in 18.3% of all contacts because **used gloves** were not removed before performing care activities that necessitated strict aseptic precautions. Failure to change or remove contaminated gloves was a major component in the poor compliance with hand-hygiene and carried a high-risk of microbial transmission. The study found that improving hand-hygiene compliance requires changing healthcare workers behaviour towards glove-use drastically (Girou E et al., 2004).

Taking note that the use of gloves for every patient contact (i.e., universal gloving) has been suggested as an infection prevention method to staff, and as an alternative to contact precautions, a Japanese study investigated the following. In this study, compliance with hand-hygiene and glove-use was directly observed at a 10-bed intensive care unit (ICU) in a Japanese teaching hospital, not unlike many major hospitals in any modern city.

In this Japanese study, a total of 6,050 hand-hygiene opportunities were identified. However, stating the obvious again, gloves may carry organisms unless they are changed properly. In addition, hand-hygiene is required before donning and after removing gloves as indicated in the studies in Iran and France, and yet there are scarce data regarding glove changing and hand-hygiene in this Japanese universal gloving setting. In trying to overcome the problems of a nonrandomized observation, a before-and-after study was conducted. The study data was evaluated and the effect of better education of healthcare workers and feedback regarding hand-hygiene was analysed.

The study published the following alarming results: "Overall, hand-hygiene compliance steadily increased from study period 1 (16.1%) to period 5 (56.8%). There were indication-specific differences in the baseline compliance, the degree of improvement, and the reasons for noncompliance. There were decreases in the compliance with universal gloving and the incidence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*."

The Japanese study concluded: "It is difficult to properly perform glove-use and hand-hygiene in a universal gloving setting, given its complexity. Direct observation with specific feedback and education may be effective in improving compliance." (Kuruno, Kasahara and Mikasa, 2017).

Concluding remarks

Intensive care units are by nature highly technical spaces. These areas have never been considered "patient-friendly," since it took care of critically ill patients and was an arena for specialists of the medical fraternity. Recently, however, thoughts around this have begun to change due to the growth of calls to "humanize intensive care" across Europe. What is key in this matter is that patients in this mass situation (instead of the rare occasion) are increasingly made to feel that when they enter the ICU, it is the last time seeing their families ever again. Consider the enormous implications this could have on the psychology of the patient, who, after laying in hospital for over 12 to 30 days, may not have a chance of recovery and ever seeing his family again. In reverse, the health practitioners may see the severe ARDS patients in much the same way as terminal cancer patients, but with the added risk of being highly infectious. This stand-off between maximum care and minimum care due to exposed risk to the hospital caregivers has not been properly assessed. Include in this the fact that no family member will ever hear the last complaints of their loved ones in ICU, and coupled with that, their bodies will be disposed of like Ebola cadavers with no autopsies, then clearly this can lead to problems. That the red flag for medical negligence or preventable hospital-acquired secondary infections adding needlessly to the death statistic of Covid-19 patients in ICU has not been raised is in itself alarming and proof that fear overrules ethics. As Dr. Pradeep Ramachandran says: "All elective procedures were canceled. Clinics were canceled, and the era of the televisit had begun. These were not normal times, I realized. We don't fall short of PPE in normal times. We don't run out of essential medications and ventilators in normal times. We don't have discussions about rationing care in normal times." (Ramachandran et al., 2020)

The prevalence of HAI and appropriate hygiene which is PATIENT-CENTRED (not caregiver centred) is extremely vague and lacking in the current pandemic. One hears regularly about the frontline workers and PPE used to protect themselves against exposure to Covid-19 while they are working with ICU wards filled to capacity with highly infectious patients. These are not Cancer ICU patients, nor comatose accident patients, nor 3rd-degree-burn patients or normal organ failure patients. In that case, the standard precautions and cleaning of wards and health care workers are understandable. There is no great risk to hospital staff in such NORMAL ICU practice. However, in the case where every single patient in ICU now represents a real threat to infection of staff, it is not clearly discernible where the lines of enough hygiene is drawn and how this is educated. Cleaning bed-pans or assisting in toilet matters for patients, often with diarrhoea in the COVID situation, incessant coughing, and other related complications leaves one shuddering to think how often such changes occur or whether HAI's are now conveniently or accidentally ignored. The life-threatening dangers of secondary infections, acquired in the hospital, is not well documented nor studied as all deaths in a Covid-Ward are conveniently written off as "due to Covid".

References

- Ghorbani, A., Sadeghi, L., Shahrokhi, A., Mohammadpour, A., Addo, M. and Khodadadi, E., 2016. Hand hygiene compliance before and after wearing gloves among intensive care unit nurses in Iran. *American Journal of Infection Control*, Vol: 44, Issue: 11, pages e279-e281
- Bardi T et al., 2021, Nosocomial infections associated to COVID-19 in the intensive care unit: clinical characteristics and outcome. *European Journal of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases* (2021) 40:495–502
- Coleman V, (1996), *How To Stop Your Doctor Killing You* (Kindle Edition), How To Stop Your Doctor Killing You. European Medical Journal, Publishing House, Trinity Place, EX32 9HJ.

De Mortel, T. 2008, Utilising health promotion theory to improve hand hygiene in the ICU: A pilot study, *Data Australian Critical Care*, ISSN: 1036-7314, Vol: 21, Issue:1, Page: 56

El Guerche-Seblain C et al., 2020, Incidence of hospital-acquired influenza in adults: A prospective Surveillance study from 2004 to 2017 in a French tertiary care hospital, *American Journal of Infection Control*, pp 1–6

Girou E., Chai S.H., Oppein F., Legrand P., Ducellier D., Cizeau F., et al., Misuse of gloves: the foundation for poor compliance with hand hygiene and potential for microbial transmission?. *Journal of Hosp Infections*, 2004; 57:162-169

Kuruno N, Kasahara K, Mikasa K, 2017, Hand hygiene compliance in a universal gloving setting, *American Journal of Infection Control*, Volume 45, Issue 8, pp 830-834,

Ramachandran P, et al, 2020, Powerless in the ICU Perspectives: from ICUs in the Face of Coronavirus Disease 2019, *CHEST*, Volume 158, issue 3

S.H. Lo, C.Y. Lin, C.T. Hung et al., 2021, *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 104 (2021) 15–18

Sax H, Allegranzi B, Chraïti MN, Boyce J, Larson E, Pittet D. , 2009, The World Health Organization hand hygiene observation method. *American Journal of Infection Control*; volume 37:8, pp 27–34.

Wendel Garcia P.D. et al., 2020, Prognostic factors associated with mortality risk and disease progression in 639 critically ill patients with COVID-19 in Europe: Initial report of the international RISC-19-ICU prospective observational cohort, *EClinicalMedicine* 25 100449